

A Study of Social Mobility, Measure of Class and Prestige in India

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Abstract: The paper examines the social mobility and stratification in India taking into account the Indian philosophical term *guna* or qualities described in the *Sankhya* system, believed to work on every matter living or nonliving. The paper also examined the foundations of ancient Indian stratification in terms of *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra*. The highest position to *Brahmans* as a social group may be a matter of self-ascription propagated through an organized propaganda with vested motives. Several ancient texts put *Brahmins* at the top of social hierarchy did not corroborate with the social systems and practices existing today and in the ancient past or any period of history. In fact, such issues remained thoroughly full of dogmatism, skepticism aimed at cheating and misleading. Moreover, *guna* or qualities such as *Rajas*, *Tamas* and *Sattva* cannot remain constant in terms of *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra*. They kept changing and orienting depending upon mutual interactions between the living world and ecosystem. Therefore, every person witness changes in status in a temporal and spatial manner. Therefore, the social mobility described by sociologists cannot be mere linear always, however, there are all possibilities that social mobility may be erratic, zigzag, and even cyclic because status and power change in a temporal and spatial manner.

Key words: *Social Mobility; Ancient Indian Social Classification; Measurement of Social Class: Caste and Varna Based Hierarchy*

Introduction

Society and Culture in India have been truly magnificent, diversified, and vast. The vastness of society and culture lies in its multi ethnicity, religion, language, and intellectual development (Malika, 2007). Development of society and culture in India could be divided into prehistoric to modern (Bayly, 1999). The culture of modern India is a complex blend of its historical traditions, influences from the effects of colonialism over centuries and current Western culture - both collaterally and dialectically (Sen, 2005). *Social mobility* is the movement of social constituents, including individuals or social groups, or any other categories of people within or between social strata in a society, causing change in the social status and hierarchy.

Vedic society in India considered by several historians as without divisions of roles and there was no development of economy. People were free to select their roles according to their attitudes and attributes and despite patriarchy and a tribal form of governance. There was no caste and Varna formation as they happened in the post Vedic period (Sharma R. S., 2005) (Sharma R. S., 1960). The Vedic Society appeared to be an egalitarian society. It would be noted that most texts, including *Aranyakas* or *Upanishads*, *Epics*, *Puranas*, and *Smriti Granthas* were compiled during the post Vedic periods.

The richness of ancient Indian literature and texts could be easy sources for studying and presenting a chronological account of *social mobility* in India. There are sufficient literatures available to us along with several existing social systems and practices that may enable us a scientific evaluation and study of the social mobility in India. A social change cannot take place overnight and in any case it never replaces all practices of the ancient past. India is a living

civilization and its several systems are still intact and very much in practice. Therefore, the study of Indian society in any retrospective manner cannot be separated from its contemporary practices in entirety.

It can be said that traditionally gender did not make any issue in most ancient literatures and it has been more used by modern sociologists. It can be attributed to the fact that women did not write any history and male may have not preferred to write a history of women. Or there may be a case that gender may not have been any issue in the past or may be deliberately ignored by ancient male scholars. Anything can be a possibility. In any case, it can be said that kings and scholars remained part of ancient literatures. Females did become a part of the mythology. So the question does arise that why farmers, laborers, workers, and traders did not become any appropriate mention in most of ancient literatures. The same thing can be said about Buddhist and Jain literatures. The bulk of social life always remained evolved around those farmers, labourers, workers, and traders. Social life at any stage of human civilization never evolved round the kings and scholars, however, they are prominently mentioned in most literatures.

The caste system in India has been a more rigid system that has been attributed by hierarchy, endogamy, territory, and to great extent biology. In a study of the caste system sociologists should not ignore the distinct biology of the different social groups and caste exhibited those biological characteristics also due to endogamy. A lion, tiger, panther, cat, or puma despite belonging to same species did not engage in any sexual act mutually. They must be knowing that this would be absurd. They can produce cubs after mutual sexual interactions. However, they avoid such things, despite sharing a common territory. Different castes

also come to acquire a distinct biology due to persisting endogamy, profession, and trade. Every caste developed some specific practices and systems. They became able to do so despite sharing a common territory. Despite living in a same village different caste did have different needs and objectives. Due to democratization, urbanization different people of different castes came in close contacts despite they have to get grouped in the name of caste. Why caste became so important, so much so that now most progressive people advocate to abolish the caste system. Many such so called progressive people do engage in inter caste and inter religious marriages. They may be also exposing or putting the distinct qualities and biology of different castes to a dangerous proposition knowingly or unknowingly. It would cause a disorganization of the society that may lead to fall of control and order in the society. It has also resulted in growing conflicts between an urban and rural society, even between people belonging to the same caste and went to reside in any urban areas from any rural areas. The traditional value system getting eroded while new values have not a strong agency to implement them. The government so far not capacity to regulate such a huge population and almost a lost case in any case. In such a situation breaking or erosion of caste system would further lead to disorganization.

If we analyse a caste system before independence or urbanization it would appear that in a village there was almost an egalitarian caste society. There was no any major social or economic rankings because income level and living standard were almost at par with each other. However, there were rankings in terms of age, gender, and levels of relationships. This balance started to get eroded after people started moving out of the respective villages and getting engaged in certain business or employments. There was a marked change in income, living standards, status, and power. Perhaps this was the greatest danger before the caste system not the inter caste marriage. Preference for a sexual preference or having multiple choices could be a reason behind people preferring inter caste or inter region marriages. Such behaviour and tendency may be termed as undisciplined and irresponsible, that emerged as the root cause of divorce, desertion, and domestic violence.

India became a closed society due to the emergence of a rigid caste system and featured by endogamy however, prior to that there existed an open, liberal, and flexible social system that may be referred as the *Varna System*. However, many western scholars have regarded the *Varna System* being based on colour of the skin. Even in ancient times, marriages or any sexual activities leading to a childbirth were regarded as absurd and so much so that such children were termed as *Chandals* and *Malechs*. *Chandals* and *Malechs* were considered as dangerous for the civilization. The ancient social classification in terms of *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra* may be within the same Varna System especially within the white complexioned

Aryan Group of people or race. There are also different versions about Shudra being not existed and just first classification being existed and marriages within those three social groups were allowed, however, there were certain protocol followed even in case of those marriages. It was considered necessary because of different upcoming of boys and girls of those three social classifications leading to a situation different boys and girls possessing different qualities. However, marriages with Shudra was thoroughly rejected. There are all the possibilities that due to fall of Varna System, dislocation, and migration different castes emerged in different point of time.

Marriage served as an important institution for both upward and downward motilities and allowed among top three social groups. Possession of knowledge was preferred in addition to power, wealth, health, and labor. An individual in possession of knowledge, power, wealth, health, and labor could enjoy the all-possible virtues of the creation. *Sanskrit* regarded as scholarly language and individual having difficulties in Sanskrit, considered low in status. There is a mention in *Atharvaveda* that people should avoid visiting Kasi and Magadha because people's inabilities living there to properly pronounce *Sanskrit*.

Social Mobility caused mainly due to factors such as motivation, achievements, failures, education, skill, training, migration, industrialization, urbanization, legislation, politicization, and modernization. In fact, not the entire community or group benefitted because movement of some individuals belonging to different social groups. If due to job and political reservation some individual become a high rank officer or politician and acquired knowledge and wealth, therefore it could not apply to the entire group or community. Therefore, social mobility is more relevant at the individual level because of the slow rate of reversible and irreversible movements.

Aim and objectives:

The basic aim of this paper would be to enrich the available sources on *social mobility*. It would expedite the descriptive possibilities of *social mobility* in ancient India. *Social mobility* considered as a great tool for establishing a just and egalitarian society and creation of anomie and therefore could have both positive and negative aspects. The contemporary study of *social mobility* required a global approach. However, due to economic growth or decline, in some particular area people there would be accordingly benefitted or troubled. It is the best tool to eliminate social inequality. Concepts of studying *social mobility* have changed its course in the age of neo sociology. New sources of information introduced and existing testimonials and concepts vigorously tested. However, all those required presentation according to a modern concepts, culture, and tradition of sociology. Therefore, this study would aim to study *social mobility* with modern aspects. The basic features of *social mobility* now additionally influenced by democracy, liberalization, privatization, globalization, and

technological breakthrough. The ethnic, lingual, and geographical barriers are fast eroding in the age of information technology. New models of *social mobility* would be required. The aim was to provide a new and higher dimension to the subject, students, and academicians.

Statement of the problem

Several misconceptions persisted about social mobility and social strata in India. Caste alone cannot be a social stratum unlike the *Varna System* in ancient or medieval time. So far, we studied a linear model of the *social mobility* that may be horizontal and vertical and even upward and downward mobility. However, linear structure is an easy expression and if things would be analyzed scientifically, those most motilities may appear never constant, ever changing that would unwise arrange as mere linear. Because, there are all possibilities of them are being erratic and zigzag. To some extent they may be even cyclic.

A data gap existed about *social mobility* in Indian culture. Unlike the caste system that mostly regarded as a rigid and inflexible system, there was tremendous mobility within the four classifications largely based upon individual qualities and behavior. Many sociologists in India and abroad made a great mistake in describing *Caste* and *Varna* as same or close. However, *Brahman* as a caste is different than *Brahman* as a *Varna*. The same could be said for other classifications.

Scientifically the qualities, behavior, and attitude of an individual depended upon the biology in addition to the ecosystem and socialization. The modern science has also described the Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid (DNA) as carrier to qualities from one generation to another. Even various theories of mutation did confirm that the mutation is caused due to possession of certain qualities and behavior in sustain manner and that could lead to changes in the DNA. The *Sankhya* School of the Orthodox Indian Philosophy described the individual qualities in terms of *Rajas*, *Tamas*, and *Sato*. The three remained embedded in the form of a rope just like DNA and exhibited different properties. The *sato* are white in colour, illuminating, and creates happiness. The colour of *rajas* are red and it is regarded as motion, action. The *tamas* are black in colour and attributed by foulness and moment of inertia. The *Sato* is the state of equilibrium which is disturbed by the *rajas* as motion and action arises. Then *tamas* rises to arrest the *rajas* and established the state of equilibrium. One property rises over another and again they come to a state of equilibrium or balance. The whole creation living or nonliving usually works according to the appropriate or misappropriate movement and orientation of those three properties. Every human being is also affected by those movements of properties and their status changes accordingly. The possession of certain knowledge, power, wealth, and status of an individual depended upon the movement of those three properties. While studying the social mobility and

classification such scientific, philosophical foundations cannot be ignored.

Shudras, *Varnashankaras*, *Chandals*, and *Malechhs* are some ancient distinctions that may have lost relevance today amidst however, certainly used as certain derogatory remarks. *Social mobility* within a caste has not been reported or studied adequately. In the contemporary world the study of social mobility cannot be restricted mere to caste and Varna systems. It has wide open many foundations ranging from race, culture, geography, gender, income, profession, living standard, status and power. Any one in isolation of other foundations cannot define the social status of an individual or social group. Caste and Varna cannot be taken as one class and therefore, the formation of class goes beyond the consideration of a caste and Varna system. Even children born out of inter caste or inter religious marriages cannot be grouped together in one particular caste, Varna, or even class. Even within a family does not mean that all family members are class equals. .

In the modern era, the rigid caste system losing it features such as engagement in common and traditional work or profession, endogamy, lingual and cultural barriers. No son or daughter of a particular caste could always engage in the traditional work of his or her own caste. In addition, they also set aside the lingual rigidity and using Hindi and English despite having different native language and using common technology and tools. Although such are mostly urban phenomenon, however rural areas and villages also getting affected. It required studying social mobility under the premises of such transformations.

Social mobility now days cannot studied amidst the four broader classifications of *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra* despite the fact that all those kind of people still existed, however, get intermingled and may be termed as politicians, bureaucrats, scholars, business man, workers, and soldiers. However, political and business class appeared more powerful than all others. Therefore, being a *Brahman*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra* would not have any relevance in studying the social mobility.

Class retains its original Marxist connotation of ownership and control of productive resources and is indicated by measures of wealth and income. Status refers to position in society and this usage retains the Weberian sense of access to life chances based on a constellation of social and cultural factors like education, family background, associations, lifestyles and expectations. Class and status, although analytically distinct, are empirically closely intertwined. This interwoven character has led to these dimensions of economic and social advantage being subsumed into the categorization of 'social class'. Social class describes the position of a person or group of persons occupies in society and it designates access to social and economic resources and to value life experience. This abstract construct is originally and essentially sociological.

In empirical studies, it requires valid and measurable indicators.

Overview of literature:

Intergenerational occupational changes of roles, taking place so rapidly in India therefore several literatures focused such issues in their studies (Chakravarty, 2013) (Azam, 2013). Education could be also a factor of social mobility (Das, 2013). Castes experienced greater mobility on average than the tribes did as shown in the study of *Rajiv Sethi* and *Rohini Somanathan* that explained them using a model in which individuals have social identities that determined the nature of competition for public goods from the state (Somanathan, 2010). In fact, whatever we talk about social mobility in terms of changed occupation and role are more symbolical with the term labor mobility (Singh, 2006). *Divya Vaid* studied the patterns of female and male intergenerational class mobility in India; and provided a comparison of these patterns over time (Vaid, 2005). *Partha Nath Mukherji* described social mobility and social structure in terms of conceptual-methodological re-orientation (Mukherji, 2012).

Gregory Clark and *Davis, Zach Landes* studied caste and class dichotomy of the social mobility in India for a period 1860-2012 and found that using surname distributions, long run social mobility rates for the elite and underclass groups in India can be compared with those of other societies such as Sweden and the USA (Landes, 2010). *Kaivan Munshi* and *Mark Rosenzweig* studied the low caste mobility and India and found that due to the existence of sub-caste networks that provide mutual insurance to their members (Rosenzweig, 2009).

Rig Veda has mention about two *varnish as Arya* and *Dasa* and in addition, it mentioned about three divisions of society Brahmins (priests), Kshatriya (warriors) and Vis (common people), however *Purussukta* also mentioned the fourth category *Shudra* (Sharma G. S., 1979). Manusmriti mentioned other categories such as *Chandal*, *Mlech*, and *Nishad* that considered even worse than *Shudras* (Bhatt, 2007).

Several scholars put their opinion that there was no certain or fixed division of role and labor, however, any individual performed all four actions according to circumstantial requirements (Sharma, 1951). Several scholars said that though four Varnas were there, however, there was no distinction such as lower or higher, or intermediary among them (Mandal, 2010).

It is believed that later during Circa 230 B.C.E to Circa 700 A.C.E all four *Varna* arranged in a hierarchy. According to some other opinion, Varna means color and, therefore, perhaps the division of society were based on fair and dark colors respectively. *Hutton (1963:66)* expressed possibilities that this color distinction in some way associated with race, however, contrary to that *Ho- cart*

(1950:46), said, the color had a ritual and not a racial significance.

Scholars like *Risley, Ghurye, Majumdar*, etc., in terms of racial factors, also explain the origin of castes, but it cannot be said that castes are the sub-divisions of varnas. The origin of castes has nothing to do with varnas, though in the process of development of castes, they came to be associated with varnas. The hierarchy of castes and the mobility of a caste came to be stated in Varna terms. Brahmin as a Varna and Brahmins as Caste were two different entities. *Brahmins* could be divided into different castes and sub castes however, Varna cannot.

According to (*Hsu, 1963:96*), *Varna* provided a framework that conditioned all Indian thinking about and reaction to caste. *M.N Srinivas* also suggested that *varna* provided a common social language that held good for India as a whole, i.e., it enabled ordinary men and women to grasp the caste system by providing them with a simple and a clear scheme applicable to all parts of India. He further held that the importance of the *varna* system consisted in that it furnished an all India frame for castes occupying the lower stairs tried to raise their status by taking over the customs and rituals of the top castes (Srinivas, 1962). Such mobility would have established a common culture all over India. Under the influence of the British, the westernization replaced Brahmins to the second place, whereas British and Landlords acquired the first place. However, Brahmins regained their hierarchy after independence due to *Pandit Nehru*, his dynastic rule largely supported his own caste men, and therefore the Brahmins progressed towards modernity and acquired urban wealth. They flourished as teachers, bureaucrats, writers, cinematic poets, artists, and religious preachers. However, post mandalization of the Indian politics, they again replaced to the second place.

Varna is from the root 'varna' that means choice according to inherent traits. According to behavior functions, and roles one person could move upward, downward or horizontal in different class identified as four Varna and the mobility was liberal that is without barriers. Such mobility could enhance or degrade social status, power, and control of an individual. The three gunas or qualities described in Indian Philosophy such as *Satto, Razas*, and *Tamas* could be attributed to those four *varnas* in one manner or another (Sharma C. , 1960).

Hutton says that the concept of Varna is often confused with the concept of caste or *Jati* although caste and Varna have different meanings. The Varna seems to have been originally the four classes. In Vedic times, the line of demarcation between the various classes not considered essential. A *Kshatriya* could become a *Brahman* (Hutton, 1963),

Ghurye described *varna* as distinction and talked about color-based classification of the *varna system* as *Arya* and *Das* (Ghurye, 1932). *Ghurye* adopted the racial theory of the origin of the *varna system*.

M.N Srinivas put the opinion that the caste system is a very complex organization and not necessarily identified by the varna system. The distinction between the caste and varna system is that the caste is a local group, whereas the varna system has an all India basis. Similarly, there is no mobility in the caste system, whereas the varna system is mobile (*Srinivas, 1962*). According to him, the varna system conceals the diversity between the caste system of one region and that of another.

The mythological origin of *Brahman* from the mouth of the *Brahma* or the creator, the *Kshatriya* from his arms, the *Shudra* from his feet. *Vaishya* expected to support the other two *varnas* and himself by agriculture, and the *Shudra* to serve the other three *varnas*. *Manusmriti* also attested those origins (*Bhatt, 2007*). According to *Manu Smriti*, the four *Varnas* have been created from the limbs of the creator. To protect the universe, different duties and occupations were assigned to the different *Varnas*. *Brahman* Varna has been regarded as the supreme creation of God. *Manu* has asserted that the *Brahman*, the *Kshatriya*, the *Vaishya* and the *Shudra* are the only *Varnas* in existence and there is no fifth Varna.

The codes of *Gautama*, *Bodhayana* and *Apastamba* have references regarding heredity, connubiality and commonality in the context of the caste system. Thus, the four Varna was separated from and related to each other by a set of laws based on two cardinal principles of division of labor and synthesis. The *Smritis*, such as *Manu*, *Vishnu*, *Yajnavalkya*, *Brahaspati* and *Narada*, report cases of mixing of castes and numerous violations of codes.

According to *Sorokin*, there is no society that is closed (Caste System in India) and no society that is completely open (Class System). He further contended that no two societies are exactly same forward movement allowed or discouraged. Further, the speed of movement or change may differ from one period to another. The rate of change depends upon the level of modernization of a given society (*Sorokin, 1959*).

As defined by *Barber*, social mobility either refers to movement, upward or downward between higher or lower social classes; or more precisely, movement between one relatively full time, functionally significant social role and another that is evaluated as either higher or lower (*Barber, 1957*).

The most practiced conceptual views about social mobility suffered from originality and hardly sanctioned *social mobility* models in caste systems. There could be levels of *social mobility* from the micro level to macro level. Several evaluations of *social mobility* remained influenced by certain bias and also lacked required empiricism. Therefore, the study of *social mobility* required expedition at different levels, such as individual and small social groups instead of macro structures like caste, a category,

such as upper, middle, and Dalits and also in terms of gender or minority.

This particular survey of literature established the need to expedite the explanatory possibilities of *Social Mobility* in India's not to be restricted to ancient foundations. Unlike ancient past foundations of modern day social mobility keep changing rapidly. In a democratic set up nothing is taken as guaranteed. The comparative aspects would open new resources that would contribute significantly to neo sociology. The frequent change of status and power at individual levels has been evident, however, still it formed a constant strata. However, if there is a degree of stability at individual or generational levels in the strata of business class, however, the same level of stability is not found in any other strata of political, bureaucratic, and labor class.

Research questions of hypothesis

1. *What were the factors, models of social mobility in ancient India?*
2. *What is the scope to describe a cyclic mobility with both reversible and irreversible features?*

Research methodology

There are many methods of measuring a social class for both generational or intra generational and inter-generational social nobilities. However, functionalist and conflict sociologists disagree on which objective criteria to use in measuring social class (*Barkan, 2014*). There has been an agreement or a common view is found among different sociologists that usually there four classes existed such as upper, middle, working, and lower. However, those broad categories are also divided into few sub categories. People are generally classified according to one or more criteria, such as their occupation, education, and/or income.

Functionalist sociologists rely on measures of socioeconomic status (SES). A measure based on occupation, education, and income favored by functionalist sociologists as an indicator of social class position, such as education, income, and occupation, to determine someone's social class. Sometimes one of these three variables is used by itself to measure social class, and sometimes two or all three of the variables are combined to measure social class. When the occupation is used, sociologists often rely on standard measures of occupational prestige.

Despite SES's usefulness, conflict sociologists prefer different, though still objective, measures of social class that take into account ownership of the means of production and other dynamics of the workplace. The conflict sociologists delineate social class on the basis of several factors, including the ownership of the means of production, the degree of autonomy workers enjoy in their jobs, and whether they supervise other workers or are supervised themselves (*Right, 2000*).

Commonly chosen indicators include occupation, education, income, residential address, organizational rank or classification. Less frequently used as barometers are type of housing, condition of tenancy, ownership of cars, televisions and other consumer durables. The prestige of occupation is a powerful measure of social class because it largely encompasses these other factors and because people will normally provide occupational information fairly willingly. Occupational prestige provides a measured indication of the total advantage, social and economic, typically enjoyed by people. Occupation is a highly visible fact designating a person's relation to the productive process of the economy and indicating where authority is held and material rewards go. Educational qualifications, typical income, probable wealth, security, authority and autonomy and conditions of work are inherent characteristics of occupations. The prestige accorded occupation is found to take this into account (Danie, 1984).

A survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire to measure the social prestige of different professions. Participants were asked to rank against a scale of 1- 5 against different parameters and different variables.

A generational and intergenerational mobility survey were conducted against variables such as income, living standard, education, and location of habitation such as urban and rural.

Findings

So far, social mobility largely presented in terms of class and in models such as vertical and horizontal whereas vertical movements could be upward and downward. The sociologists have propagated only linear models, however, there could be other models of the movements that required adequate presentation in the terms of academic customs and cultures of the modern sociology. The ancient system of social classification such as *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra* were largely dependent upon individual qualities and traits. There was no system of forced or bondage labour as they emerged during post Vedic periods at different stages. So much so that ancient philosophy considered status of an individual being affected the manner three properties such as *Sato*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas* get oriented in a temporal and spatial manner.

The society was not globalized and the social status does not matter or focused properly. Everyone was engaged in their occupation irrespective of any consideration of social status or power. Even today if there would be multiple choice before an individual, then only he or she would be doing or engaging in an occupation best he or she can do. No one can become *Brahmans*, *Ksatriya*, *Vaishya*, and *Shudra* by choice, however, by his or her qualities and traits would ensure a status. An objective should be to make an egalitarian society and in such a case every individual must be treated equally irrespective of age, gender, and health. However, it is an ideal case as there is no egalitarian society

nowadays. The irrational distribution of power and wealth can lead to deviance and may further contribute to the construction of different strata.

Any change in social status, position usually caused due to vertical movement, however, with horizontal movement, social status, position remains constant despite changes in occupation or affiliation. Vertical mobility is a phenomenon in the open society, whereas closed society is more attributed to horizontal mobility. However, the situational change because of democratization, liberalization, privatization, and globalization the scope of social mobility and its study acquires a global dimension. There is sufficient evidence that now caste and *Varna* cannot be regarded as prominent strata for social mobility. There are numerous changes of status and position within a caste system and family. The caste could be no more regarded as a symbol of hierarchy in fact caste based hierarchy largely now could be termed as a self-ascribed because of members of certain caste of their own considered themselves superiors than others.

In ancient period the social mobility was possible among all the four classifications such as *Brahmins*, *Kshatriya*, *Vaishyas*, and *Shudra*. In fact, *Brahmins*, *Kshatriya*, *Vaishyas*, and *Shudra* entirely indicated the traits, qualities, and attributes. A scholar was regarded as *Brahman*, a brave and barrier regarded as *Kshatriya*. *Parsurama*, despite being a born *Brahman* became a universal barrier or soldiers. *Vishwamitra*, despite being born as *Kshatriya* became a great sage and *Valmiki*, despite belonging to a low social order regarded as a great scholar. Therefore, with such examples it could be assumed that all those classifications were liberal and not rigid. Even those classifications were not affected by gender and age. A person of any age and gender can assume the position in the appropriate strata because of possessing certain qualities.

The four classifications such as *Brahmins*, *Kshatriya*, *Vaishyas*, and *Shudra* can be also sometimes symbolized with knowledge, power, wealth, and labor respectively. However, keeping all those four knowledge, power, wealth, and labor mutually aloof and apart from each other would not make any sense. All those needed to be possessed by an individual or social group in a sustained manner to ensure a higher rank or position.

In addition, those social rankings could change in day-to-day social transactions depending upon circumstances. In a particular situation a mighty king could become and behave like a beggar needing help from others. An individual as a teacher enjoys, respects and privileges while the same person out of his class loses all his virtues and privileges.

In a closed system a social status is ascribed and that was the case with the caste system and also to *Varna* System to an extent. It means position is fixed at birth and the chances of altering your social status during the life time are very

unlikely. An open system allows movement within the strata.

It was extremely significant that almost 84 percent participants believed that caste and Varna do not symbolizes any social prestige now. Mostly believed prestige dependent largely on character, values, behavior, and conduct. It has nothing to do with income and living standards. Most participants also talked about creating strata for values, traits, behavior, and conduct also.

The average prestige scores for various occupations was measured for physician, 55; college professor, 34; community based elementary school teacher, 64; letter carrier, 47; garbage collector, 28; and janitor, 22. The prestige scores for bureaucrats, politicians, and other government employees were respectively at 42, 39, and 40. More surprisingly, people gave farmers and housewife highest ranks in social prestige. Females usually commanded higher prestige compared to male.

The generational mobility as per status and prestige almost remained constant. However, it showed drastic or deep upward and downward movement as shown in figure 2 and 3.

Figures

Figure 1: Reversible and cyclic mobility in ancient India

Figure 2: Generational Mobility

Figure 3: Inter Generational Mobility

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